

References

1. M. C. PATEL, J. R. SHAH and R. P. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
2. ARTHUR I. VOGEL, *A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry*, Third Edition, Longmans, pp. 176.
3. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
4. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
5. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
6. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1924, **16**, 111.
7. K. S. BRATKI, A. T. RANE and M. B. KABADI, Proceedings of Symposium on the Chemistry of Coordination Compounds, Agra, Feb. (1959), Part III, p. 87.

Gravimetric Determination of Platinum with P-Dimethylaminoanil of 3-Phenanthryl Glyoxal

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IN our previous communication¹, chelates of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Pt(IV), Mn(II) and Fe(III) with *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-Phenanthryl glyoxal (ligand) have been prepared and characterised. It has been observed that ligand forms dark coloured chelates which are more or less soluble in acetone except Pt(IV) chelate. Ligand reacts quantitatively with Pt(IV) in acetone to give light grey precipitate. It is therefore thought worthwhile to carry gravimetric estimations of Pt(IV) with the ligand and to note the effect of various compounds present.

Preparation of the solutions: Reagent (*p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal²) was dissolved in acetone to prepare approximately 0.01M solution. Stock solution of H₂PtCl₆.6H₂O was prepared in acetone and standardised gravimetrically by the procedure described by Vogel³.

A known volume (2–65 ml) of platinum chloride was taken and diluted to 75–100 ml and the precipitant solution was added slowly with constant stirring; grey precipitate of platinum (IV) chelate is formed immediately. After allowing to stand for 15 min., the precipitate was filtered through sintered glass crucible, washed several times with dry acetone, dried in oven and weighed as Pt(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)Cl₄. Several experiments were performed by using different volumes of platinum chloride solution.

From the experimental results, it may be concluded that *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal can effectively be employed as a gravimetric

reagent for platinum. In the gravimetric experiments error found was of the order 1–2%. The precipitate is insoluble in 75% acetic acid acetone, ether, benzene and carbontetrachloride. *P*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal is tested as gravimetric reagent only for Pt(IV) in acetonic medium, hence this method may be regarded as of limited applicability. However, reagent is quite effective in 75% acetic acid medium also. Moreover, the reagent is quite specific in presence of nickel chloride, cupric chloride and bromide, cadmium chloride and acetate, ferric chloride, zinc chloride, manganese chloride and silver nitrate.

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References

1. R. K. UPADHYAY and R. C. SAXENA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, communicated.
2. R. K. UPADHYAY and R. C. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Communicated.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Group Limited, London (1969).

Gravimetric Determination of Cadmium with the Ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline

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THE ligand has recently been used for the gravimetric determination of Cu(II) by the authors. In the present investigation the same ligand has further been used for the gravimetric determination of cadmium. Investigations have indicated that at pH 7.5 to 10 of the ligand, it reacts with Cd²⁺ ions giving precipitate of insoluble metal complex. The cadmium complex after settling is of orange red or brown red colour. The element analysis shows that the mole ratio of the metal to ligand is 1 : 2. The method is useful even if 0.5 mg of cadmium is present.

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade and the ligand was prepared by the method of Bagulev and Elvidge¹.

Element Analysis—Ligand	%C	%H	%N
Found	58.9	3.9	17.5
Required	59.3	3.7	17.3

The following stock solns. were prepared.

- (1) 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline...about 0.1% sodium salt soln. of the ligand in NaOH of pH 7.5 to 10.